

HYDROGEL CORE FLEXIBLE MATRIX COMPOSITE (H-FMC) ACTUATORS

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ABSTRACT

The hydrogel core, flexible matrix composite (H-FMC) actuator is a muscle-like device that employs soft, pH-responsive hydrogels to directly convert chemical energy into mechanical work. Preliminary modelling of the H-FMC concept has revealed that the use of composites in this way can improve the useful work output of a hydrogel by over 1500%. However, this analysis assumed the use of a solid hydrogel core within the H-FMC actuator. In order to improve the speed, and thus power output of the H-FMC actuator, this core must be composed of micro or even nano-dimensioned elements. The work presented shows that actuation performance benefits can be realised by switching from commonly investigated fast actuating systems composed of fibres or beads, to a solid core containing coiled channels. Although unconventional, such a configuration has been manufactured, proving its feasibility. This work also shows, via finite element analysis (FEA), that for actuation speed and blocking stress performance an increased number of channels is preferential. Furthermore, moderate coiling of the channels has a positive effect on actuation free strain. Increasing the tightness of the coil to its extremes has a beneficial effect on actuation speed, but leads to a reduction in free strain potential. It is anticipated that this work will guide the design of H-FMC actuators into the future, with such devices having great potential in a range of applications including robotics and morphing structures.

1 INTRODUCTION

A recent investigation by the authors into the creation of biomimetic photo-actuating structures [1] has led to the development of a concept for a muscle-like composite actuator (Figure 1) [2]. This artificial muscle, referred to as an H-FMC actuator, employs a soft, pH-responsive hydrogel material to mimic natural muscle's ability to directly convert chemical energy into mechanical work. pH-responsive hydrogels are hydrophilic polymers which are protonated or deprotonated as a result of changes in the surrounding pH. This results in a fixed charge being established on the polymer, which leads to a change in the polymers equilibrium state of swelling. The H-FMC actuator is composed of a flexible matrix composite tube, with a hydrogel core that swells when exposed to solutions of varying pH. Preliminary modelling of the H-FMC actuator has revealed that the concept can improve a hydrogel's useful mechanical work output by over 1500% [2]. Further benefits from the H-FMC concept may include increasing the robustness of the hydrogel material, and improving actuation strain recovery.

However, the H-FMC model that was employed in this earlier work assumed the hydrogel core to be a solid structure. For the realisation of an actuator with reasonable speed, and thus power output, careful

consideration needs to be given to forming the hydrogel core with an optimised micro or even nano-dimensional structure. Investigating this structured core is the focus of the work presented.

The investigation begins with a review of the challenges associated with creating hydrogel actuators, allowing an understanding of the requirements for the structured core. This is followed by an overview of the operating principles, and resulting benefit of hydrogel composites. These first two sections allow for the key design parameters of the structured hydrogel core to be established. From here, finite element analysis (FEA) is conducted to build the case for the merits of competing hydrogel structural arrangements, with consideration of the manufacturability of each. Finally, further FEA is conducted on variations of the resulting optimal configuration, such that the effect of varying different design parameters can be investigated. The work concludes with a brief discussion on the study's limitations and future work.

Figure 1: The H-FMC actuator concept. The actuator is shown with a cut-out to reveal the internal hydrogel. (a) Displays the actuator in its unactuated condition at $\text{pH} \ll 4$. (b) In this unactuated state the osmotic pressure (P_{os}) generated by the hydrogel is zero, as the polymer has no fixed charge, as depicted in (c). (d) The hydrogel is now exposed to an environment of $\text{pH} 10$, the swelling inducing osmotic pressure is now greater than zero, as the acidic groups on the hydrogel polymer have been deprotonated, as depicted in (e). (f) This osmotic pressure is coupled through the anisotropic FMC, and cylindrical geometry to produce a contracting actuation force and stroke (arrows). Figure adapted from Dicker *et al.* [2].

2 A BRIEF REVIEW OF HYDROGEL ARTIFICIAL MUSCLES

In many respects pH-responsive hydrogels have great potential as artificial muscles. They are soft, with a typical Young's modulus (E) under 1 MPa, produce free strains of over 100%, blocking stresses of up to 4 MPa, and mimic natural muscle's ability to directly convert chemical energy into mechanical work [3]. However, there are many challenges that have hindered and continue to hinder the development of hydrogels as practical actuation materials. These limitations include slow, dimension-dependent actuation rates, mechanical fragility and the practical challenges of converting three-

dimensional swelling into a targeted actuation and controlling the delivery of the chemical energy for doing so. As a result, the application of pH-responsive hydrogels has largely been limited to drug delivery and microfluidics [3-4].

The most prominent challenge facing the development of macro-scale hydrogel actuators is in improving the response speed. Hydrogel swelling speed is dictated by the rate with which water can diffuse into the hydrogel, a process governed by an inverse square relationship between diffusion time and the hydrogel's smallest dimension [5-6]. With the water diffusion coefficients for hydrogels ranging from $1\text{-}10\ \mu\text{m}^2\text{s}^{-1}$, even millimetre-sized hydrogels take hours to actuate [7].

To address this drawback, significant attention has been given to producing both micro and nano-dimensioned hydrogel components. This may be in the form of films, fibres, beads or by adding porosity to macroscopic gels [4, 7–10]. However, porosity leads to a reduction in force generating capacity, and great difficulty exists in turning films, fibre or beads, into practical actuator solutions that both maintain fast action, whilst generating significant actuation force. For example, two actuators were developed by Brock *et al.* which employed hydrogel fibres prepared from poly(acrylonitrile) (PAN) filaments with diameters of $10\ \mu\text{m}$ [11]. Although the simulated response times of the fibres were of the order of 0.1–0.2 seconds, actual response times when fibres were bundled together in a practical and controllable actuation configuration was of the order of 8–12 seconds. These results highlight the difficulty of developing a device to expose hydrogel actuators quickly to reacting solutions, and that the bundling of micro-dimensioned fibres hinders diffusion rates. This was further confirmed by Lee *et al.* who showed that PAN yarns (diameter $210\ \mu\text{m}$) composed of 300 nano-fibres with diameter $700\ \text{nm}$ still only actuated at a maximum rate of 20%/s [12]. Work on actuating single PAN micro-fibres by Choe and Kim [13–14] and polyacrylic acid (PAA) nano-fibres by Gestos *et al.* [7] found that full actuation stress and strain could be achieved within one second. Clearly there is a speed benefit to reducing the dimensions of these materials, but arranging these units such that the diffusion of the activating species/solvent is not hindered, whilst providing enough units to provide meaningful force is challenging.

More recent examples of actuators that aim to address this challenge include the work of Tondu *et al.* [15–18] and Santulli *et al.* [19]. In these examples, McKibben actuators containing hydrogels as the internal pressure source were manufactured. These actuators consisted of an internal elastomeric tube (a permeable membrane in the work of Santulli *et al.*) constrained externally by an un-bonded fibre weave or braid. In the work of Tondu *et al.* the hydrogel took the form of micro-beads, while Santulli *et al.* experimented with a variety of beads and fibres. Although these represented some of the most practical macro-scale hydrogel actuators developed to date, with the generation of axial contractions from a compact package, rate of actuation was still low. In both cases actuation took place over periods ranging from tens of minutes to hours. Santulli *et al.* investigated the difference in swelling rates between the hydrogel fibres or beads constrained only by a permeable membrane, and with the addition of a stiffer braid. An order of magnitude increase in swelling rate was observed with the addition of the constraining braid. Although no explanation is offered for this observation, one could hypothesise that packed hydrogel beads and fibres do not create a structure that maintains its porosity under loading. It is this process that is investigated in Section 5 of this work, and forms a key consideration for the development of the optimum hydrogel structure.

3 THE OPERATING PRINCIPLES AND BENEFIT OF THE H-FMC CONCEPT

Before investigating optimal hydrogel structures for use in a flexible matrix composite, or McKibben type actuator, it must be recognized that there is more to be considered than simply improving the actuation rate by maintaining minimum diffusion distances. In fact, it must firstly be understood that there is more benefit to hydrogel–composite integration than the conversion of a three dimensional swelling into an axial contraction, eliminating the buckling constraint of slender actuators. The real benefit of hydrogel–composite integration appears to lie in the potential to improve the useful work output of the hydrogel [2]. To this end, this section outlines the operating principles of the H-FMC actuator concept, so that the full list of considerations for developing an optimal hydrogel core structure

can be understood. In so doing, this section also serves to highlight the value of exploiting the anisotropic properties obtainable with composite materials for the development of multifunctional materials.

3.1 Hydrogels

Hydrogels are hydrophilic polymers with the ability to swell through the absorption of water. pH sensitive hydrogels are composed of polymers containing acidic or basic groups. The extent of protonation of these acidic or basic groups is dependent upon the pH of the surrounding environment, relative to the log of the proton association constant for the functional polymer. As the hydrogel becomes deprotonated (for acid groups) or protonated (for basic groups), a charge is introduced to the polymer. This fixed charge has a number of effects on the equilibrium state of the hydrogel, but the most significant is the interaction of this charge with all the free ionic species in solution. This interaction results in a differential being established between the ionic concentration of the solution inside the hydrogel, and in the surrounding environment. In an attempt to limit this differential an osmotic pressure is established, driving water into the hydrogel, and causing it to swell. As the hydrogel swells, the concentration or density of the fixed charge is reduced, limiting its interaction with free ionic species, and reducing the osmotic potential. The swelling continues until an equilibrium is reached between the osmotic pressure and elastic restoring force of the strained hydrogel. Large increases in performance can be achieved if an actuator can be designed to limit unwanted volumetric expansion, thus maintaining the critical fixed charge density. This process is the cause of both the force-stroke relationship observed with hydrogel actuators [20], and the improved performance generated by using composites to constrain one axis of a hydrogel's swelling [21].

3.2 Flexible Matrix Composite (FMC) Actuators

Flexible matrix composite (FMC) actuators are similar to the McKibben actuators described previously, although in the case of the FMC, the external fibre weave or braid is integrated into the elastomeric membrane forming a composite material. The McKibben actuator was developed in the 1950's, while the FMC actuator was not investigated until over 50 years later by Philen *et al.* [22]. The benefit of the FMC concept over the McKibben actuator is in the ability to explore a vast range of fibre orientations and laminate configurations. For simple balanced composites, the actuator can be designed to either elongate or contract upon the application of an internal pressure, by dictating a specific layup with orientation θ , with respect to the axis of actuation (see Figure 1b). The actuator extends for $\theta > \pm 55^\circ$ and contracts for $\theta < \pm 55^\circ$. Contracting FMC actuators take advantage of the large Poisson's ratio (ν) of the FMC and the geometry of the cylinder to produce stresses larger than those generated by the internal pressure. For cylindrical, thin-walled (internal radius/wall thickness great than 10 [23]) FMC actuators, the axial stress is half the circumferential or hoop stress, thus allowing the Poisson's ratio of the FMC to provide a mechanical advantage, and contraction of the actuator.

3.3 Hydrogel Core Flexible Matrix Composite (H-FMC) Actuators

The H-FMC actuator concept increases a hydrogel's useful work output because it harnesses the mechanical advantage of the contractile FMC actuator, while limiting the hydrogel's unused swelling, maintaining its critical fixed charge density. A challenge facing the contractile H-FMC concept is the requirement to undertake work in overcoming both the hydrogel osmotic pressure and the hydrogel material stiffness. By comparison, a pneumatic FMC actuator only has to overcome the internal pressure.

3.4 Hydrogel Core Flexible Matrix Composite (H-FMC) Actuators Benefits

Analytically derived force-stroke curves for a series of H-FMC actuators, including both extension and contraction actuators are presented in Figure 2a [2]. Here, the benefit of the concept is clearest when examining the absolute blocking force generated, compared to a bareline hydrogel (black line). Figure 2a also demonstrates some of the differences between FMC and H-FMC actuators. For a FMC actuator, one would always expect to see contraction actuators (fibre angles $\theta < 55^\circ$) with higher blocking force than extension actuators, but with the H-FMC actuator this is not necessarily the case. For example, it is observed that the $\theta = 80^\circ$ actuator outperforms the $\theta = 30^\circ$ actuator. This result is due to the greater

restriction that the $\theta = 80^\circ$ actuator places on increasing hydrogel volume, which ultimately is more significant to actuator performance than the high Poisson's ratio offered by the $\theta = 30^\circ$ actuator. However, buckling is of concern for the $\theta = 80^\circ$ extension actuator, thus contractile actuators are generally seen as the desired configuration for the H-FMC actuator.

The area underneath a force-stroke curve gives a measure for the useful mechanical work output of the actuators. Figure 2b displays results from this calculation over the full range of fibre orientations for a series of actuator sizes, compared to the value for a baseline hydrogel of the same dimensions. The improvement is shown to be substantial, and of increasing significance for larger actuators.

Figure 2: (a) Absolute force-stroke chart for a variety of fibre orientations (where θ relates to fibre angle with respect to the axis of actuation) for 100 mm long, 6 mm radius (r) H-FMC actuators. The black line shows the force-stroke relationship for a bare hydrogel of the same dimensions. (b) The increase in useful mechanical work output from the H-FMC actuator over the bare hydrogel as a function fibre wrap angle and radius. Figure adapted from Dicker *et al.* [2].

This improvement in useful actuation work is put into context in Figure 3. The performance is compared through the index of stroke work per unit volume, as per Huber *et al.* [24]. This index encompasses the dimensionless stroke work coefficient C_s , the ratio of maximum work done to the product of the blocking stress σ and free strain ϵ . It lies between 0 and 1, and is taken as 0.5 for the hydrogel actuators.

Figure 3: Actuator comparison in terms of stroke work per unit volume. The performance shift from the baseline hydrogel (red) to the H-FMC concept (green) is indicated by the arrow. The yellow region is the actuation performance of muscle. Figure adapted from [2], with all non-hydrogel data obtained from Zupan *et al.* [25].

4 OBJECTIVES FOR AN OPTIMALLY STRUCTURED HYDROGEL CORE

Considering the information presented thus far, a series of points can be established as objectives for the design of the hydrogel core structure.

- Speed: with an inverse square relationship between actuation rate and diffusion distance, diffusion distances must be minimised, and remain minimised throughout actuation. This objective means maintaining diffusion pathways through the core, even under loading.
- Stress: Core structure must be able to maintain external loading of as much of the maximum osmotic pressure as possible. With porous structures this constraint, representative of the blocking stress scenario, is likely to be related to the buckling of slender components.
- Strain: Maximise the ratio of radial stress (radial strain) to axial stress. This can be achieved by minimising unused swelling and reducing the axial stiffness of the hydrogel core.
- Manufacturability: Limit the design to simple fibres, beads or channels, geometry that can be manufactured.

5 COMPARING FIBRES/BEADS WITH CHANNELS

Table 1 shows FEA results designed to compare the merits of having a hydrogel core composed of fibres or beads, to the inverse solution, one composed of channels. Although the FEA attempts to capture the complexity of the nonlinear geometry, it is simplistic in the material properties applied (linear elastic), and in the nature of the osmotic pressure, which is a constant, unaffected by changes in hydrogel volume.

This simplified analysis indicates that for equal hydrogel volumes, channels give a better result than packed fibres or beads. Firstly, there are regions in the channel configuration where the initial diffusion distance is half that of the fibres/beads design, which could give a fourfold increase in swelling speed for these regions. Secondly, the fibres/beads design has initially small contact areas between the components. As the components begin to swell these points become stress concentrations, which result in large deformations, which do not contribute to radial strain, but serve only to close the flow pathways through the core and reduce the fixed charge density. As a result, the increase in hydrogel area for the fibres/beads design compared to the channels is 12%, despite the channels model giving 29% more radial strain. This increase in area causes a reduction in the charge density and resulting osmotic pressure, only serving to exacerbate the difference in radial strain between the two configurations. This additional change in area for the fibres/beads design is largely expended closing the diffusion pathways, which are reduced by 39%. In contrast, the channels open under loading, with a 24% increase in area being observed.

Although this preliminary analysis clearly indicates that channels are preferential to fibres or beads, there is no consideration of how the configuration performs in a blocking stress scenario, where buckling of the internal structure may occur. There must also be consideration of how this structure performs when it is axially compressed during actuation. In this situation, the slender walls formed between adjacent channels almost certainly buckle. Although this buckling would lead to a desirable reduction in axial stiffness, it may also damage the hydrogel, close the flow channels and affect the ability of the structure to provide radial strain.

One way to avoid this axial buckling is to coil the channels, which will transform the straight slender walls into spring-like elements, eliminating the column buckling mode. A rendered image displaying this concept is displayed in Figure 4a. This concept also has the beneficial effect of reducing both axial stiffness and diffusion distances. The minimum diffusion distance in the coiled concept is now a diagonal path between adjacent channels. The added benefit to diffusion rates can also be recognised through the increased surface area created. Although the coiled channel concept appears to be preferential, consideration must be made regarding the manufacturability of the concept.

Table 1: 2D, Nonlinear FEA comparison of 19 fibre or bead packed configuration and a 19 channel configuration. Both configurations have identical initial hydrogel area, to which a constant osmotic pressure (0.35 MPa) is applied at the free surfaces. The hydrogel core, diameter 14 mm with Young's modulus 1 MPa, is surrounded by a stiffer material 0.5 mm thickness, with Young's modulus 8 MPa.

6 MANUFACTURABILITY

Although manufacturing of the coiled channel concept is more challenging than packing the H-FMC with fibres or beads, it is still achievable. Figure 4b and 4c show some early examples of 0.5 mm diameter channels in polyurethane-PAA interpenetrating network hydrogels. This unpublished work was conducted with the assistance of Professor Geoffrey Spinks, Dr Sina Naficy and Dr Holly Warren of the University of Wollongong, Wollongong, Australia. The hydrogels are formed around fibres which are later removed.

Figure 4: (a) Rendering to display the concept of coiled channels. Here 19 coiled channels with diameter of 1.38 mm are created in a 14 mm diameter hydrogel cylinder. The coils have a radius of 0.5 mm and a pitch of 10 mm. (b) An example of 19 slightly coiled channels placed in an un-swollen 15 mm diameter hydrogel. (c) A heavily coiled channel in a swollen hydrogel, here the extraction of the channel forming fibre has slightly torn through the hydrogel, suggesting that there is a fabrication limit to coil tightness.

This manufacturing process affects the cross section of the channels (in the radial plane) so that they are no longer circular, but become bent ellipses. Analysis to examine the effect of this imperfection is needed, combined with analysis of any benefits that may result from having more tightly coiled channels, such as reduced diffusion distance and axial stiffness.

7 DESIGN CONSIDERATIONS FOR A COILED MICRO CHANNEL HYDROGEL CORE

Before examining the effect channel coiling has on actuator performance, the effect of increasing the number of straight channels and their size must be investigated. Figure 5 shows free strain results from 3D FEA of H-FMC actuators subjected to constant osmotic pressure (solid lines, left axis), and blocking stress results, constrained by buckling failure, from 2D FEA (dashed lines, right axis). A constant osmotic pressure (0.35 MPa) is applied to all hydrogel surfaces in the analysis. In the 2D blocking stress model, eigenvalues are extracted from the analysis of a hydrogel core with identical properties to the free strain analysis, but with the addition of a blocking pressure, equal in magnitude but opposite in direction to the osmotic pressure, and applied only to the outer circumference of the hydrogel. Cores with 1, 7 and 19 straight channels are investigated, as these are configurations for which a circular packing configuration exists where all circles are fully constrained, ensuring an equal distribution of material around each channel. All results are presented as relative values compared to an equivalent H-FMC actuator with a solid core.

The horizontal axis of Figure 5 attempts to capture the inverse square relationship between diffusion distance and actuation rate through introduction of an actuation speed index (units $1/\text{mm}^2$). It is observed that there is a reduction in free strain potential as more and larger straight channels are added to the core. However, for a given actuation speed, improved performance is obtained by having more straight channels, both in regards to free strain performance and in increasing the onset of buckling in the blocking stress analysis. For the 19 straight channel configuration the analysis was unable to determine eigenvalues for such blocking stress analysis. Figure 5 also shows the complicated effect channel coiling has on free strain and actuation speed. The coiled channel performance is investigated by taking a straight 19 channel configuration (infinite coil pitch) and measuring free strain and diffusion distances as the pitch is reduced (Figure 5, Coiled data set).

The analysis indicates that smaller holes lead to an increase in blocking stress potential compared to fewer large holes, given equal actuation speed index. This result is due to the reduction of the slenderness of features which form the structured core. It is more complicated to understand the relationship between channel size and quantity in regards to free strain performance. On the one hand, taking material out of the core reduces the H-FMC actuators potential to do radial work, a disadvantage to free strain

performance. However, it also reduces the H-FMC actuators potential to do axial work, an advantage to free strain performance. Figure 6 suggests that unlike the blocking stress potential, the free strain potential of uncoiled configurations is almost exclusively dependent on the cross sectional area of the core, with the number of channels added having no substantive effect.

Figure 5: ABAQUS obtained FEA analysis. (●—● left axis) Free strain analysis conducted on 3D model, hydrogel core diameter 14 mm by 20 mm, with linear elastic material properties of $E = 1$ MPa, $\nu = 0.3$, to which a surface osmotic pressure of 0.35 MPa is applied. The core is surrounded by 4 ply (0.125 mm ply thickness), balanced, symmetric $\theta = \pm 45^\circ$ laminate, fibre direction $E_1 = 150$ GPa, matrix direction $E_2 = 11$ MPa and $\nu = 0.4$. (—■— right axis). Blocking stress analysis conducted on a comparable 2D model, indicating the relative onset of buckling. Selected unscaled deformation plots, contoured with radial strain are also shown.

Figure 6: Relative free strain results (from ABAQUS 3D FEA, as described in Figure 5) for both coiled and uncoiled configuration. It is observed that the performance appears almost entirely dependent upon the cross sectional area of the hydrogel core, with no dependency on the number of channels. The failure of the coiled configuration to follow this trend suggests there are other parameters dictating its performance, with the resulting reduction in axial stiffness likely to be the most significant contributor.

Figure 7 examines the effect of coiling in more detail by showing the 3D FEA results for free strain (left axis) as a function of the level of coiling of the channels, with images of the core cross section. Although increasing the tightness of the coil (high coil radius to pitch ratio) leads to a desirable reduction in axial stiffness, it also increases the severity of the bent ellipse cross section of the channels. The result is that there is a limit to the level of coiling that is desirable for a given material and configuration.

Figure 7: Free strain results (left axis), and related cross section images for varied levels of channel coiling (from ABAQUS 3D FEA as described in Figure 5). Actuation speed index (right axis), with through coil cross sections showing minimum diffusion distance.

From this analysis it can be concluded that for a fixed hydrogel area, a structure containing as many moderately coiled channels as possible, is optimal.

8 STUDY LIMITATIONS AND FUTURE WORK

The comparative nature of the modelling presented in this work – although sufficient for guiding the early development of the H-FMC concept – is a significant limitation of the work presented. Future work includes refinement of FEA modelling to better capture non-linear material properties and geometry. Ultimately this work aims to develop H-FMC actuator demonstrators to validate the analysis undertaken.

It should also be noted that we can only hypothesise that the trends observed in this analysis will continue beyond the range of parameters investigated. For example, although it is reasonable to expect the benefit observed for a channelled structure over fibres or beads to hold as the number of channels/fibres is changed, the relative benefit is likely to vary significantly.

Furthermore, this investigation has only covered simple structures that were deemed manufacturable. Although the resulting coiled channel configuration is thought to be optimal, it is only so in comparison to a solid core, a straight channel core, or one composed of packed fibres or beads. Optimisation unconstrained by current manufacturing constraints may result in different structures being established, which could potentially be produced in the future using additive manufacturing techniques. Such analysis would form valuable future work.

9 CONCLUSIONS

The material properties of pH-responsive hydrogels make them strong candidates for use in the creation of artificial muscles. However, there are a number of challenges which have prevented pH-responsive hydrogels being used in such applications, including the difficulty of controlling the supply of the chemicals species which power the actuation, and most prominently, the slow, dimension dependent response. In previous work by the authors the concept of the biomimetic control of H-FMC actuators has been developed as a means to improve the feasibility of hydrogel actuation, in large part by employing composites to increase a hydrogel's useful work output. In doing so the value of exploiting the anisotropic properties obtainable with composite materials for the development of multifunctional materials has been shown. However, to improve the speed of response, and thus power output of the H-FMC actuator, an investigation of micro or nano-dimensional internal hydrogel structures was required. Previous studies have shown the difficulty of using such structures, whilst maintaining adequate actuation performance. In this work, it has been shown that the addition of coiled channels to the hydrogel core leads to superior performance over other manufacturable configurations such as packed fibres or beads. Further investigation has revealed that for a given hydrogel volume, the free strain performance is independent of the number of channels added. However, both speed and blocking stress performance are improved by incorporating additional channels. The coiling of the channels was found to improve free strain performance, provided the tightness of the coiling was not excessive. It is anticipated that this work will guide the design of H-FMC actuators in the future, with such devices having great potential to perform as artificial muscles in a host of applications.

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